

91. Plants were scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) after 20 continuous drought days under field conditions. TKM10, CO 31, and TKM1 showed only slight tip drying. These three rice types recovered quickly and established well when the plots were irrigated, while others showed

various degrees of drought tolerance and recovery (Table 2).

TKM10 has medium slender, white grains. Its cooking quality is good. Consumers prefer it because it is highly suitable as both raw and parboiled rice.

It is moderately resistant to gall midge, green leafhopper, and leafhopper

under field conditions and brown planthopper, whitebacked planthopper, and leafhopper under artificial conditions.

It was moderately resistant to blast (under field and artificial screening), brown leaf spot, and sheath rot. It was moderately susceptible to rice tungro virus. □

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Physiology and plant nutrition

Leaf thickness affects the estimation of leaf N using a chlorophyll meter

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Several studies recently published in international journals evaluated the use of a chlorophyll meter to estimate rice leaf N concentration with the goal of predicting the need for fertilizer-N topdressing. The accuracy of this estimation, however, was influenced by the stage of plant development, genotype, and the number of meter readings taken on an individual leaf blade. We conducted this study to determine how many point-readings were sufficient to accurately estimate the N concentration of an individual leaf and whether leaf thickness affected the estimation.

We used a chlorophyll meter (Minolta SPAD-502) to determine the SPAD

values of 20 intact IR50 flag leaves at flowering in the greenhouse. Nine SPAD readings were taken at 30-mm intervals from the base to the tip of each leaf blade. All measurements were made in the leaf margin on one side of the midrib. We then measured leaf area and determined the dry weight after oven-drying the leaves at 70°C. Specific leaf weight (SLW), which reflects leaf thickness, was calculated as the ratio of dry weight to leaf area. Leaf N concentration was determined by standard microkjeldahl digestion and distillation.

In a field study in the 1992 dry season, we took SPAD readings on the 12 uppermost fully expanded leaves at midtillering of IR72. For each leaf, mean SPAD value represented the average of three SPAD readings taken around the midpoint of the blade, 30 mm apart, on one side of the midrib. Leaf N and SLW were determined as in the greenhouse study.

Values of SPAD were closely related to leaf N concentration (see table). Increasing the number of readings from one at the middle of the blade to three that bracketed the midpoint of the leaf resulted in a significant increase in the coefficient of determination (r^2). Further increases in readings per leaf blade did not increase r^2 . Therefore, only three SPAD readings around the midpoint on one side of the midrib can provide a reasonable estimate of leaf N concentration.

Six of the 20 flag leaves that were sampled in the greenhouse had 3.72% N (± 0.04 SD), although SPAD values varied from 44.5 to 49.0. The SPAD values were positively related to SLW (see figure), indicating that leaf thickness and N concentration influence the SPAD reading. Multiple linear regression also revealed that both SPAD values and

Relationship between leaf N concentration and mean SPAD values of individual leaves as influenced by the number of SPAD readings taken around the midpoint of each leaf blade (simple regression), and the significant effect of specific leaf weight (SLW) on this relationship in the greenhouse and field studies (multiple regression).^a

Readings/leaf	Simple/multiple regression	r^2	R^2
Greenhouse (n = 20)			
1	N% = -0.49 + 0.09 (SPAD)	0.69***	
3	N% = -0.75 + 0.09 (SPAD)	0.81***	
5	N% = -0.84 + 0.10 (SPAD)	0.79***	
7	N% = -0.72 + 0.09 (SPAD)	0.75***	
9	N% = -0.69 + 0.09 (SPAD)	0.76***	
3	N% = -0.04 + 0.10 (SPAD) - 0.21 (SLW)		0.86***
Field (n = 72)			
3	N% = -0.30 + 0.11 (SPAD)	0.74***	
3	N% = 0.54 + 0.11 (SPAD) - 0.21 (SLW)		0.78***

^a *** = significant at P < 0.001.

Relationship between specific leaf weight (SLW) and SPAD values of 6 leaves with similar N concentration in a greenhouse study. ** = significant at P < 0.01.

SLW were significant independent variables ($P < 0.03$) for predicting leaf N concentration in both greenhouse and field studies. With three SPAD readings per leaf blade in each case, the proportion of variability in leaf N concentration that the independent variable accounted for increased from 81 to 86% in the greenhouse study and

from 74 to 78% in the field study when based on SPAD values alone vs the combination of SPAD values and SLW as independent variables (see table).

Using a chlorophyll meter to monitor the N status of the rice plant may provide a useful tool for managing research experiments and varietal trials where adequate N supply must be maintained in

diverse environments and on different soils. Data, however, should be interpreted with caution because the SLW can influence the SPAD reading. If leaf N estimates need to be more accurate than SPAD readings, then the SLW should also be determined. This process is much simpler and faster than using the kjeldahl method to determine N. □

Fertilizer management—**inorganic sources**

Nutrient management for cotton - rice cropping system

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Cotton *Gossypium hirsutum* L. is grown in Srivilliputtur during Feb-Mar under summer irrigated conditions following wet-season rice. A short-duration pulse is generally grown during Aug-Sep between the cotton and rice crops in this system.

We studied nutrient management for cotton - green gram - rice during 1991 - 92. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. The soil at the site represents the tract and is a sandy clay loam with low available N, medium P, and high K. Short-duration cotton variety SVPR 1 was sown during Apr 1991, and the second crop, green gram KM2, was grown during Sep 1991. This was

Crop yields in a cotton-rice system in Srivilliputtur, Tamil Nadu, India, 1991-92. ^a

Treatment			Yield (t/ha)		
Cotton 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha	Pulse 25-50-0 kg NPK/ha	Rice 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha	Cotton	Green gram	Rice
Full NPK	Full NP	Full NPK	0.78	0.33	4.1
N	Full NP	Full NPK	0.74	0.33	4.0
N	P	Full NPK	0.74	0.32	4.0
N	No fertilizer	Full NPK	0.75	0.24	3.8
No fertilizer	No fertilizer	Full NPK	0.49	0.23	3.8
Full NPK	No fertilizer	Full NPK	0.77	0.26	3.9
No fertilizer	No fertilizer	Full NPK plus preen gram stubble	0.50	0.23	4.2
LSD (0.05)			0.06	0.03	ns

^a ns = not significant.

followed by IR20, which was transplanted in Nov 1991 with different fertilizer levels.

There was a clear response when NPK was applied to cotton and green gram under rice - fallow conditions. Cotton yields with 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha and 60 kg N/ha alone were similar. In the succeeding green gram, the yield was higher when 25 kg N and 22 kg P/ha were applied, which was on par with 22 kg P/ha

alone. In this sequence, the rice crop had a uniform application of the recommended dose of NPK fertilizers. Rice yield was not affected by fertilizer treatments in the preceding crops.

These results indicate the significance of the recommended 60 kg N/ha for summer cotton, 22 kg P/ha for a pulse crop, and NPK for a wet-season rice crop in the cropping system studied (see table). □

Fertilizer management—**organic sources**

Breaking seed dormancy in *Sesbania rostrata*

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Sesbania rostrata has potential as a leguminous green manure for lowland fields in many countries. But its thick,

hard seed covering can cause problems for growers.

We tested several methods to break seed dormancy using hot water, sulfuric acid, scrubbing with sand, and scrubbing and soaking in hot water.

Scrubbing seeds with sand for 5 min and/or soaking in hot water (about 60 °C) for 15 min were not very effective.

Treating seeds with concentrated H₂SO₄

Germination of *S. rostrata* seed under different treatments.

Treatment	Observation (no.)	Germination rate (%) ^a
Control	4	12.00 ± 3.61
Hot water for 15 min	4	17.25 ± 2.77
Scrubbing with sand for 5 min	3	12.33 ± 1.70
Scrubbing + hot water	3	20.00 ± 2.94
H ₂ SO ₄ concentrated	7	94.39 ± 4.06
Fast washing	3	6.13 ± 0.72
Slow washing	3	6.13 ± 0.72
H ₂ SO ₄ diluted	3	15.67 ± 1.88

^a Mean ± standard error.